

Supporting Information

Gas Diffusion Electrodes for Electrocatalytic Oxidation of Gaseous Ammonia: Stepping Over the Nitrogen Energy Canyon

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Experimental Procedures

Chemicals

Aluminium nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), silver nitrate (AgNO_3), cerium(III) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate, ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), nickel(II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), manganese(II) nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), molybdenum(V) chloride (MoCl_5), palladium(II) nitrate dihydrate ($\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$), rhenium(III)-chloride (ReCl_3), zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) from Sigma-Aldrich were used for the preparation of compositions containing Al, Ag, Ce, Co, Cr, Ni, Mn, Mo, Pd, Re, and Zn. Iron(III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Acros Organics) was used as iron source. For copper cupric nitrate hemi(pentahydrate) ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$) from Alfa Aesar was used. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) ($(\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{NO})_n$) powder (MW-55,000 D) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All compounds except MoCl_5 (95 %) were synthesis grade (≥ 98 %). As electrolyte 1 M KOH (86.4 %, Fisher Scientific) solution was used. As NO_x gas trap 0.1 M NaOH solution was employed (Sigma-Aldrich). Both 1 M KOH and 0.1 M NaOH solutions were prepared using ultra-pure water and purified with Chelex 100 cation-exchange resin (Sigma-Aldrich) before use.

Preparation of gas diffusion electrodes

The preparation technique of gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) employed in this work has already been reported for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). The catalyst layer on Ni foam was prepared using the polymer/metal precursor spraying technique.^[1] The total concentration of metal precursors was kept constant at 1.17 M. Metal precursors were dissolved in 10 wt% PVP solution. For compositions containing only nitrate precursors, only distilled water was used for the preparation of the synthesis solution. When both chloride and nitrate precursors were employed an ethanol and water mixture in the ratio 1:1 was used for the solution preparation. The prepared solution was sprayed using a spray-coater platform, where syringe pumps enable precise volume control, with the assistance of compressed air to the spray nozzle solution is distributed in the form of small droplets (Figure S1). 2 μL of synthesis solution is sprayed onto Ni foam every 2 mm in X and Y directions. Both sides of Ni foam are covered. Ni foam is placed on a hot plate (125 °C) that enables evaporation of the solvent and formation of a continuous polymer layer with entrapped metal precursor particles. Next, polymer composite-covered Ni foam is submitted to a two-step heating procedure in a 3-zone tube furnace. First, reduction at 800 °C in 90 % Ar/10 % H_2 for 2 h is performed followed by oxidation in 90 % Ar / 10 % O_2 for 2 h. For the preparation of the gas diffusion layer the spray-coater platform was employed as well.^[2] A PEEK mesh was chosen as the substrate and hydrophobic layer for the GDE. A uniform and homogeneous layer is achieved by spraying 8 μL of ink every 2 mm in both X and Y directions on a PEEK mesh kept on Ni foam modified with the catalyst layer. For the spray ink, 1.744 g methyl cellulose (Sigma-Aldrich), 1.744 g Latex (1.1 μm , Thermo Fisher Scientific), 2.006 g isopropanol, 1.338 g deionised water, and 0.097 g TIMREX® SFG-44 carbon were mixed by using a Turrax stirrer together with a magnetic stirrer for 10 min. To improve the hydrophobicity, 0.111 g PTFE dispersion (3M Dyneon PTFE Dispersion, TF 5060GZ) was added to this ink afterward followed by mixing using only a magnetic stirrer for 10 min. After spray-coating, the Ni foam and PEEK layers were pressed together using a hot press at 130 °C and 1 $\text{mN}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The obtained GDE was then put in a muffle oven and heated under air at a rate of approximately 2 $\text{K}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ until 330 °C, keeping the temperature for 10 min and letting it cool down overnight. This enables oxidization of the pore-forming methyl cellulose and Latex and removes the residual solvents.

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Figure S1. Spray coater platform. The PVP/metal precursor solution for catalyst layer preparation or carbon-based suspension for the gas diffusion layer is moved to a spraying nozzle via a syringe pump. With the help of pressurized air, the solution is ejected from the spraying nozzle in the form of an aerosol and deposited homogeneously on the heated surface of Ni foam or a PEEK mesh respectively.

Materials characterization and product analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) based elemental mapping were obtained using a Quanta 3D FEG scanning electron microscope (FEI) operated at 30.0 kV. Overlay of SEM-EDX elemental mapping for Ni foam-based electrodes is done excluding SEM-EDX maps of Ni. Due to very intense signals arising from a much higher atomic percentage of Ni in the substrate in comparison to the multi-metal layer covering the substrate, the intermixing of coating elements is hard to distinguish when the Ni SEM-EDX elemental map is included in the overlay. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning TEM (STEM) images of AlCoCrCuFe powder were obtained using a JEOL microscope (JEM-2800) with a Schottky-type emission source at 200 kV. EDX of the particles was performed using double Si drift detectors (SDD) with a solid angle of 0.98 steradians with a detection area of 100 mm². Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) was performed with an iCAP RQ (Thermo Fisher) instrument in KED mode (collision cell mode with helium as collision gas). Before the measurement, around 1.5 mg of the sample was solubilized in 4 mL of concentrated nitric acid (36 %, Roth) and filled up to 10 mL with water. From this solution, dilutions of 0.01%, 0.1%, 1% and 10% acidified with 2% nitric acid were analyzed by ICP-MS. The average ppb values of ²⁷Al, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁷Fe, ⁶³Cu, and ⁵⁹Co isotopes were determined. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed using a Bruker D8 Discover X-ray diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) in the range $2\theta = 5\text{--}90^\circ$. The concentration of the produced nitrite and nitrate was systematically detected and quantified by using ion chromatography (IC) (930 compact IC Flex, Metrohm). The system was equipped with an anion exchange column (Metrosep A Supp 18 – 150/4.0) to separate the ionic species and an ion conductivity detector (ProfIC Detector MF) for the detection of nitrite and nitrate. 23 mmol/L KOH was used as eluent (mobile phase). The IC system was operated at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min at the column temperature of 30°C. The system was calibrated with known concentrations of nitrite and nitrate. Liquid samples for ion chromatography were filtered using a syringe filter (pore size 0.2 μm) (Agilent Technologies) before analysis. For the quantification and detection of gaseous ammonia oxidation reaction (AmOR) products, a gas chromatograph (GC) from SRI Instruments was used. As a carrier gas for the thermal conductivity detector (TCD) based analysis Ar gas was used.

Data evaluation

The current density was calculated based on the geometric area of the working electrode (Ni foam-based GDEs = 0.95 cm²) according to the equation (1):

$$j = \frac{i \text{ (A)}}{A \text{ (cm}^2\text{)}} \quad (1)$$

Potentials recorded vs. Ag|AgCl|KCl (3 M) were converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale by correcting the measured potential with the uncompensated resistance (R_u) obtained from the Nyquist plots from EIS measurements and adding the formal potential of the reference electrode according to Equation (2). The pH value (13.9) was calculated considering the activity of hydroxide in the electrolyte using the literature value of 0.766 for the activity of water (γ) (3). For conversion of potential values recorded during chronopotentiometry (CP) measurements at 100 mA·cm⁻² and 200 mA·cm⁻² R_u value obtained at 50 mA·cm⁻² was used, as R_u determination from EIS measurements at higher current densities was unsuccessful.

$$E = E_{\text{measured}} - R_u \cdot i + E_{0,\text{Ag/AgCl/KCl (3 M)}} + 0.059 \cdot \text{pH} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{pH} = 14 + \log [\text{OH}^-] + \log(\gamma) \quad (3)$$

Faradaic efficiencies (FE) of the gaseous and liquid products were calculated using Equation (4) and Equation (5), respectively:

$$FE_{(g)} = \frac{n \cdot Z \cdot F \cdot P}{i \cdot V_m \cdot 10^6} \cdot 100 \% \quad (4)$$

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$$FE_{(t)} = \frac{n \cdot Z \cdot F}{Q} \cdot 100 \% \quad (5)$$

n is the amount of product detected (number of moles, mol); Z is the number of transferred electrons; f is the gas flow in ($\text{L} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$); F is the Faraday constant ($96485 \text{ C} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$); i is the total current at the injection time (A); V_m is the molar volume of an ideal gas ($24.5 \text{ L} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ at 25°C), 10^6 is the conversion factor of ppm to vol%, and Q is the passed charge.

Flow-through cell measurements

For the evaluation of AmOR activity and selectivity a 3-compartment flow-through cell was used (Figure S2). The counter electrode compartment was separated from the working electrode compartment using a cation exchange membrane FKL-PK-130 from Fumasep. The GDE prepared according to the description above separated the working electrode compartment from the reactant gas supply compartment. As counter electrode an unmodified piece of 0.9 mm thick Ni foam ($0.7 \text{ cm} \times 2.5 \text{ cm}$) was used. Ag|AgCl|KCl (3 M) electrodes with a double junction in 1 M KOH were used as reference electrodes, and 1 M KOH was used both as catholyte and anolyte. A peristaltic pump served for the circulation of the electrolyte. The gas-tight anolyte compartment was continuously purged with Ar. After assembly of the cell, only Ar was supplied to the so-called backside of the GDE (the side that is not in contact with the electrolyte). First, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at OCP was measured from 100 kHz to 10 Hz followed by cyclic voltammetry conditioning cycles from 0 V to 0.45 V vs. Ag|AgCl|KCl (3 M), $100 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for 8 cycles (Figure S2). Conditioning CVs in the absence of ammonia gas was performed to convert the multi-metal catalysts into the (oxy) hydroxide form which is considered the active electrocatalyst surface. Then, linear sweep voltammograms (LSV) were recorded in the potential range from 0 V to 0.7 V vs. Ag|AgCl|KCl (3 M) at a scan rate of $10 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. After that, the ammonia gas stream diluted by Ar in a ratio of 1:1 (10 mL min^{-1} to 10 mL min^{-1}) was supplied to the backside of GDE. After flushing with diluted ammonia for 5 min the LSV measurements were repeated.

Figure S2. Conditioning procedure of $\text{Ni}_x\text{AgAlCrFeNi}$.

For flow-through cell measurements, the dilution ratio of NH_3 and Ar remained the same (1:1), however, flow values were increased (20 mL min^{-1} Ar to 20 mL min^{-1} NH_3) as higher pressure increased the stability of the GDE during the long-term measurement. Following EIS, CV, and LSVs, a CP measurement was performed at constant current ($50 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, $100 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$, or $200 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$) for 100 min. Liquid samples were extracted at 0, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 min since the beginning of the measurement and analyzed using IC. Gas streams from the anolyte compartment and backside of GDE were first purged through gas wash bottles filled with 0.1 M NaOH serving as traps for NO_x gases. After the gas wash bottles gas streams from the anolyte and the backside of the GDE were merged and analyzed using on-line GC by injection at the same time of liquid sample extraction (Figure S4). After the measurement, the 0.1 M NaOH solutions from the gas wash bottles were also collected for IC analysis. Ar gas was purged through a gas-tight catholyte compartment and the hydrogen gas produced during the counter-reaction was analyzed by on-line GC injecting at 10, 30, 50, 70, and 90 min since the beginning of the measurement.

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Figure S3. a) Three-electrode flow-through cell scheme, and b) self-made gas diffusion electrode with Ni foam-based catalyst layer and a carbon-modified PEEK mesh gas diffusion layer.

Figure S4. LSV measurements in the a) absence and b) presence of NH_3 gas (Ar and NH_3 mixture in ratio 1:1). LSVs recorded from 1.0 V to 1.7 V vs. RHE, $10 \text{ mV}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in 1 M KOH. The increasing number indicates an increasing potential value for the investigated reaction at $30 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, where 1 is the lowest potential vs. RHE.

Table S1. Potential shift using different catalyst compositions modified GDEs at $30 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ in the presence and absence of ammonia gas.

Catalyst layer	OER V	AmOR V	ΔmV
AgCoCuNiZn	1.700	1.376	-324
AlCoCrFeNi	1.664	1.574	-90
Ni foam	1.609	1.582	-27
CoCrMnMoNi	1.528	1.517	-12
AgCeCoNiZn	1.625	1.614	-11
CoCrFeMoNi	1.571	1.561	-9
AgCoCuFeNi	1.532	1.541	+9

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Figure S5. Flow-through cell system with on-line GC used for AmOR selectivity measurements.

Figure S6. Concentration of the formed a) NO_2^- and b) NO_3^- during CP measurements at 10 mA·cm⁻², 50 mA·cm⁻², and 100 mA·cm⁻², respectively, using a Ni_rAlCoCrFeNi modified GDE. Dashed lines are guides for the eyes.

Figure S7. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_rAgCoCuNiZn catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

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Figure S8. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_r-AlCoCrFeNi catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S9. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_r-AgAlCoCrCu catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S10. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_r-AgAlCrFeNi catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

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Figure S11. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_xAlCoCrCuFe catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S12. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_xCoCu catalyst layer of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S13. Performance of Ni foam-based electrodes investigated for AmOR selectivity: a) FE (%) and b) concentration (mmol·L⁻¹) of the formed NO₃⁻. In part a) of the graph the FE of Ni_xAgAlCoCrCu is marked as 0, as the concentration in sample 0 was higher compared with other samples. Sample 0 is extracted after LSV measurement in the presence of ammonia, but before the beginning of the CP measurement and is subtracted during FE calculations. Dashed lines are guides for the eyes.

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Figure S14. a) FEs and b) potential vs. RHE values obtained during CP measurements at $50 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for 100 min in 1 M KOH for all investigated GDEs. Dashed lines are guides for the eyes.

Figure S15. Electrode Ni-AgCoCuNiZn performance during AmOR – FE towards NO_2^- formation dependence on potential vs. RHE. For convenience, potential is only plotted in the period from 20 min to 100 min, as the first data point for FE available is at 20 min. Dashed lines are guides for the eyes.

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Figure S16. FE and corresponding E vs. RHE values obtained during CP measurements at $50 \text{ mA}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ for 100 min in 1 M KOH using a) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-AlCoCrFeNi}$, b) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-AgCoCuNiZn}$, c) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-AgAlCoCrCu}$, d) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-AgAlCrFeNi}$, e) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-AlCoCrCuFe}$, and f) $\text{Ni}_f\text{-CoCu}$ as catalyst layers in the GDEs. Dashed lines are only guides for the eye.

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Figure S17. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_i-AgCoCuNiZn catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50 mA·cm⁻² of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S18. SEM-EDX images of Ni_i-AgAlCoCrCu GDE's catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50mA·cm⁻².

Figure S19. SEM-EDX images of the Ni_i-AgAlCrFeNi catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50 mA·cm⁻² of the corresponding GDE.

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Figure S20. SEM-EDX images of the Ni₁AlCoCrFeNi catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50 mA·cm⁻² of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S21. SEM-EDX images of the Ni₁AlCoCrCuFe catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50 mA·cm⁻² of the corresponding GDE.

Figure S22. SEM-EDX images of the Ni₁CoCu catalyst layer after 100 min of CP measurement at 50 mA·cm⁻² of the corresponding GDE.

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Figure S23. XRD pattern of AlCoCrCuFe powder. Co_{0.7}Fe_{0.3} (FCC, PDF 00-048-1818, olive), Al_{0.13}Co_{0.87} (BCC, PDF 01-071-9376, red), Cu (BCC, PDF 03-065-9026, light green), Al_{1.8}Cr_{0.2}FeO₄ (Spinel, PDF 01-078-4763, dark blue), Al_{0.6}CoFeO₄ (Spinel, PDF 01-083-4769, cyan), AlCrFeO₄ (PDF 1-078-4761, orange) and Cu₂O (BCC, PDF 01-071-3645, pink).

Figure S24. FE obtained during 100 min CP measurements in 1 M KOH with Nif_AlCoCrCuFe with no ammonia supply to the backside of the GDE.

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Figure S25. FE and E vs. RHE values obtained during 100 min CP measurements in 1 M KOH with Ni_rAlCoCrCuFe: a) AmOR at 100 mA·cm⁻², b) AmOR at 200 mA·cm⁻², FE values obtained during 100 min CP measurement at the cathode c) HER at 100 mA·cm⁻², and d) HER at 200 mA·cm⁻². Dashed lines are only a guide for the eyes.

Figure S26. Flow-through cell system with on-line GC used for (NO₂) oxidation reaction selectivity measurements.

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Figure S27. FE values obtained during the nitrite oxidation reaction measurement using 0.1 M NaNO₂ solution in 1 M KOH as anolyte.

References

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Author Contributions

Ieva A. Cechanaviciute: investigation – synthesis of gas diffusion electrodes, flow-through cell measurements for ammonia oxidation, SEM measurements, TEM measurements, visualization, writing – original draft preparation. Lars M. Alfes – flow-through cell measurements, catalyst screening. Bhawana Kumari – ion chromatography measurements. Corina Andronescu: resources, supervision, project administration. Wolfgang Schuhmann: conceptualization, resources, supervision, writing – review and editing, project administration.